

1 **Lefty1 is first activated and then silenced during trophectoderm commitment.**

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7 Hand1 was activated following Lefty1 silencing. Lefty1, Hand and Nodal, a third developmental factor,
8 functioned together during embryonic stem cell lineage specification modeling the pluripotent quality of the
9 human embryo. This occurred together with downregulation of the stem cell marker Cd44 and silencing of
10 the pluripotency factor *Nanog*.

11 Citations

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1. Meno, C., Shimono, A., Saijoh, Y., Yashiro, K., Mochida, K., Ohishi, S., Noji, S., Kondoh, H. and Hamada, H., 1998. lefty-1 is required for left-right determination as a regulator of lefty-2 and nodal. *Cell*, 94(3), pp.287-297.